

HÄME PILOT

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HÄME PILOT IN SOUTHERN FINLAND

- 100 km from Helsinki and Tampere
- Covers two provinces
- Total population 372 000
- Häme Pilot Region classified as rural areas close to urban areas

Structure

1. Lessons learned
2. Main results achieved
3. Action Plan alignment and adoption
4. Pilot case study
5. Technical tools
6. Foresight tools (guides)

1. Lessons learned

- ✓ The key stakeholders and policy makers should be committed to the work in early stages of the process
- ✓ In regional development work, as a result of Polirural, there is now more interest in multi-actor and collaborative approach
- ✓ Covid has changed the way regional development planning is carried out.
 - Online meetings can be attended more easily by a variety of people which results in more diverse viewpoints in discussions
- ✓ Benefits of new interactive tools have gained interest among policymakers

2. Main results achieved

- ✓ New insights and knowledge about your region, is based on data used in SWOT analysis.
- ✓ Better understanding of data improves regional policy making
 - A regular business statistics is now being published
- ✓ New innovative tools such as SDM will be introduced

3. Action Plan alignment

Alignment with LTV4RA will make our region

- ✓ **Stronger**
 - As a result of increased development activities (by supporting businesses and improving data utilization)

- ✓ **Connected**
 - Increased networking, also including businesses, will result in continuous and more transparent monitoring system for rural ecosystem development

- ✓ **Resilient**
 - Innovation “Häme Foresight Academy”

- ✓ **Prosperous**
 - Stronger economies (bioeconomy, circular economy, tourism, wellbeing and manufacturing industry) in Häme Region form an ecosystem that nourishes business development, innovations and growth.

3. Action Plan adoption

- ✓ Häme Pilot Action Plan and foresight work has brought new insights to regional development work and has aroused interest in other regions as well.

- ✓ Action Plan has not been adopted yet

- ✓ Final seminar will be held in September/October 2022
 - Our target is to launch a group to implement the results of the project in Häme region (Häme foresight academy).

4. Pilot case study

- ✓ Selected part of the results will be published on our project website
- ✓ In addition to the the final seminar, project results will be circulated in publications (partly in Finnish).

5. Technical tools

- ✓ Regional SDM
 - We are studying to utilize system dynamic modelling in new projects
- ✓ Semex
 - Text mining needs more practise and know-how
- ✓ Rural Attractiveness Explorer
 - We will study the tool
- ✓ Digital Innovation Hub
 - Finnish [AgriHub](#) started 2022
- ✓ Atlas of Best Practices

6. Foresight tools (guides)

After the project, we will contribute to the use of PoliRural foresight tools among policy makers and regional authorities

- ✓ Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)
 - how to deal with big change of work and living
- ✓ Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)
 - how to prepare the following CAP on time
- ✓ Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)
 - how to integrate GD into all regional development
- ✓ The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change
- ✓ D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology
 - guide to foresight work
 - Häme foresight academy - a platform to collect and disseminate data for foresight work)